

EXCITATION AND ADAPTATION IN THE VERTEBRATE ROD PHOTORECEPTOR

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ABSTRACT

The excitatory processes and the reactions of the rhodopsin photoproducts in vertebrate rods are summarized, and an adaptation model of the rod is outlined. The transmitter factor Q describes the ability of the discs to release a transmitter carrying the signal from the site of light adaptation to the plasma membrane of the receptor. If Q decreases appropriately when the background light intensity increases, the response range of the rod is preserved and the rod obeys Weber's law. This kind of receptor adaptation is experimentally observed in several species. A photoisomerization in a disc apparently affects the release of a transmitter also in neighbouring discs. The background light also affects the neuronal network of the retina, preserving the response range of the ganglion cell. After an exposure bleaching an appreciable fraction of rhodopsin the sensitivity of the rod returns in two phases: a faster intermediate adaptation and a slow opsin adaptation. After a rather small bleach the photoresponse is fairly well preserved (mainly Q -adaptation), but large bleaches cause a strong reduction in the response range. Different experimental methods utilized when correlating rhodopsin photoproducts and intermediate adaptation are discussed.

KEY WORDS: VISION; RODS AND CONES; RHODOPSIN; ADAPTATION, OCULAR

FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES OF THE ROD

The basic structure of the vertebrate rod is schematically shown in Fig. 1 A. The photopigment, rhodopsin (or porphyropsin), is located in the membranes of the outer segment discs, and the primary visual event is the photoisomerization of the 11-cis retinal chromophore of rhodopsin (42). The rhodopsin molecules in the disc membrane are highly oriented, so that the elongated chromophore, with its chain of conjugated double bonds, is parallel to the surface of the disc membrane. Normally, light enters the retina in the direction parallel to the long axes of the cylindrical outer segments. Thus the quanta are effectively caught by the chromophores. On the other hand, the disc membrane is in a liquid crystal state, so that the rhodopsin molecules are free to rotate and diffuse in the plane disc membrane (13, 15, 32, 36).

After the initial photoisomerization from the 11-cis to the all-trans form of the rhodopsin chromophore, triggered by the absorption of a photon, the rhodopsin molecule passes through several rapid conformational changes. These changes result in short-lived photoproducts (hypso-, batho-, and lumirhodopsin and metarhodopsin I). These intermediates

are spectroscopically different from the parent rhodopsin and can thus be identified and studied at very low temperatures (e.g. 45) or by using extremely fast photometric methods (15, 39). The end product of this rapid process is metarhodopsin II (M II, λ_{\max} 380 nm), to which the isomerized rhodopsin appears to be quantitatively converted in less than 0.1 sec at a physiological temperature. The shift of the absorption maximum from the 500 nm of the rhodopsin to the 380 nm of M II thus involves a true bleaching of the molecule, which loses its »colour» in the visible spectrum. During the whole sequence of events from rhodopsin to M II the chromophore retinal remains in the same oriented position in the disc membrane. From the state M II there is a further, but much slower decay of the molecule. Visual excitation of the rod is somehow linked to the stages between rhodopsin and M II.

The slow decay reactions after a large bleach proceed in many species (including the frog) according to Baumann's scheme (4).

In the frog these processes take 30—60 min

Fig. 1. A. The dark current of sodium ions in a retinal rod. The discs are indicated by the vertical lines in the outer segment. B. An equivalent circuit of the sodium current. E is the source voltage (e.m.f) due to the sodium pump, G is the conductance of the open sodium channels in the outer segment plasma membrane, R_e is the small resistance of the extracellular path. A possible leakage conductance in parallel with the sodium channels is also shown. Stimulus light elicits the receptor potential by decreasing the voltage U_e .

at 10–15°C. The end results of the process are vitamin A (retinal) and the specific protein, opsin. The process can be described by the first-order rate constants k_1 , k_2 , k_3 , and k_4 . However, in the disc membrane the decay of M II is not really a first-order reaction, because k_1 and particularly k_2 increase when decreasing the amount of rhodopsin bleached (17) to such an extent that practically no metarhodopsin III is observed when bleaching only 2% of the rhodopsin (1, 17). In addition, the external Ca^{2+} , which apparently influences the internal concentration of this ion, affects k_1 and k_2 so that with small bleaches these are increased when the Ca^{2+} concentration in the incubating fluid for the retina is increased (14). Furthermore, the conversion of retinal to retinol is known to be enzymatically controlled and thus k_4 is not a true first-order process. The decay sequences after both small and large bleaches on the isolated perfused frog retina may be described by a modification of Baumann's scheme above (17):

Here the reactions 1, 2 and 3 depend on the amount of rhodopsin bleached.

After the decay sequence regeneration occurs, with addition of new 11-cis retinal to opsin (42). After strong bleaches of frog rods this retinal is obtained from the pigment epithelium (38) but small stores in the rods are apparently utilized in physiological conditions (1, 8, 17).

The plasma membrane of the photoreceptor is hyperpolarized by light (7). In darkness the membrane is quite permeable to sodium ions, and illumination decreases this permeability (41). In darkness the sodium pump drives sodium ions out of the inner segment, back to the rod through the sodium channels in the outer segment plasma membrane, and through the cilium back to the inner segment, as seen in Fig. 1 A (26). The light causes hyperpolarization by closing sodium channels. Since the effect of light is to isomerize chromophores of the rhodopsin molecules in the discs, and the discs are discontinuous with the plasma membrane in the rods, there must be some mechanism whereby excitation is transmitted from the disc to the plasma membrane. This has been assumed to be brought about by the release of an internal transmitter,

presumably Ca^{2+} ions, from the discs (27). A number of experimental observations support this assumption, as well as results of micro-injections of Ca^{2+} ions into the rod outer segment (11).

Light-sensitive enzymatic reactions, like rhodopsin phosphorylation (34) and the reduction of cyclic GMP concentration (see e.g. 10), have been revealed in retinal rods. These observations suggest that information transmission in the rods is not a straight-forward process, as is assumed in the conventional calcium hypothesis. In many cell activation processes both Ca^{2+} and cyclic nucleotides participate in the signal processing, one substance acting as a primary messenger and the other(s) controlling the activation by forming negative (and also positive) signal feedback loops (37).

A light stimulus initiates the process of seeing, but a light exposure also strongly affects the sensitivity of the cell, i.e. it activates the processes of adaptation. In the presence of a background of steady light the sensitivity to a superimposed light stimulus is reduced: *background adaptation*. After exposure to a strong light the recovery of the sensitivity is slow and gradual, particularly if a relatively large fraction of the rhodopsin has been bleached: *dark adaptation*. In the next sections these processes will be examined in terms of a simple model of the outer segment adaptation (29), and we discuss possible mechanisms of adaptation.

BACKGROUND ADAPTATION

Theoretical considerations

A simple equivalent circuit for the light-dependent sodium current of the rod outer segment is shown in Fig. 1 B. E is the source voltage (e.m.f.) due to the sodium pump. The conductance G of the outer segment plasma membrane is the product of the number of open sodium channels and the conductance of a single channel. Let each photoisomerization on the average cause a release of q molecules of internal transmitter, and let these molecules have an average life time τ before inactivation. Thus in the case of a step of light stimulus the light intensity I gives rise to an increase in the concentration of this internal transmitter,

$$\Delta c = Q I, \quad (1)$$

where the transmitter coefficient Q is proportional to both q and τ . The transmitter molecules are assumed to bind rapidly and

reversibly to the sodium channel molecules, thereby causing closing of these channels. The rate of channel closing is proportional to the transmitter concentration c and to the number of open channels. Thus the sodium current decreases in the light and the plasma membrane hyperpolarizes, leading to a decreased synaptic transmitter release in the receptor terminals. The receptor potential U is the decrease of the voltage U_e across the resistance of the extracellular path (R_e in Fig. 1 B). It is observed when measuring the transretinal voltage change due to the light stimulus after the elimination of other electroretinogram (ERG) components by using, for instance, aspartate. According to the above assumptions the relative photoresponse as a function of the stimulus intensity I is (28, 29)

$$\frac{U}{U_{\max}} = \frac{I}{I + I_H} \quad (2)$$

where U_{\max} is the maximum photoresponse and I_H is the stimulus intensity determining the sensitivity U/I at low stimulus intensities: $U/I = U_{\max}/I_H$. Eq. 2 is the Michaelis equation known from the enzyme kinetics. In Fig. 2 this function is presented in a log.-log. diagram. The curve, called the *operating curve*, has two straight asymptotes, one in the 45°-direction (small linear responses) and another horizontal (saturation). The crossing point of these lines, defined by the parameters I_H and U_{\max} , determines the position of the operating curve. Adaptation processes in the rod outer segment change these parameters, displacing the operating curve while, according to the model, the shape of the curve stays constant (29). The values of the parameters I_H and U_{\max} in the dark-adapted state are denoted I_h and U_m .

Light-adaptation of the receptor means changes in the stimulus-response function caused by an increase or a decrease in the continuous background illumination. The necessity for such changes is apparent. A background light I_B produces according to Eq. 1 a constant concentration of internal transmitter, $c_i = Q I_B$. This keeps a fraction of the sodium channels closed and dilutes the effect of the transmitter molecules released by a stimulus light added to the background. Without the presence of any adaptation processes the background light would displace the operating curve downwards and to the right, as seen in Fig. 2. However, the downward displacement (the decrease of $\log U_{\max}$) would be disastrous to the range of measurable stimulus intensities. Like any detector or meter,

Fig. 2. Operating curves, log photoresponse versus log stimulus intensity, as calculated according to the model. In the dark-adapted state (the top-most curve) the measurable range of stimuli is two log units, as indicated by the arrow (the dashed horizontal line refers to the minimum measurable photoresponse). A background light $I_B = 31.6 I_h$ ($\log I_B/I_h = 1.5$) displaces the operating curve along the 45° -line, reducing the measurable intensity range to ca. 0.3 log units. The middle operating curve corresponds to the rod in the same background illumination when Q has been reduced 1.5 log units.

the photoreceptor can measure the stimulus intensities over a limited range of intensities which elicit responses above the noise level but below saturation (two log units in Fig. 2). The calculated displacement of the operating curve in Fig. 2 due to the background light $I_B = 31.6 I_h$ is such that the receptor saturates almost as soon as the noise level has been exceeded. The essential goal of light-adaptation is to preserve the response range when the background intensity increases. A simple way to achieve this goal is to decrease the transmitter release factor q . This reduces the displacement in the 45° -direction due to the transmitter background $c_i = QI_B$. Besides, the operating curve moves to the right, because the increment in transmitter concentration, $\Delta c = QI$, brought about by the stimulus light I , decreases proportionally. The resultant displacement in the presence of the background light $I_B = 31.6 I_h$ is also seen in Fig. 2 when Q is reduced 1.5 log units. The range of measurable intensities is almost as extensive as in the dark but shifted towards higher values. Contraction of the pupil displaces the operating curve exactly like the decrease of Q . The pupil reacts more rapidly but its regulating capacity is rather small, about 1.2 log units in man.

Because of the predominantly horizontal movement of the operating curve the adaptation processes have been customarily studied

by recording changes in the threshold intensity I_t corresponding to a small chosen criterion response U_c . However, it is important to notice that the decrease of U_{\max} also affects I_t . When the chosen criterion is small enough, the change in log threshold is a sum of the horizontal and vertical displacements of the operating curve.

A functional goal of light-adaptation could be that contrasts in a scenery appear constant even when the illumination level varies. This is achieved when the threshold I_t increases according to Weber's law

$$I_t/I_0 = 1 + I_B/I_D, \quad (3)$$

where I_0 is the absolute threshold intensity in the dark and I_D is a constant («dark light»). This equation gives a constant ratio $I_t/I_B = I_0/I_D$ when $I_B \gg I_D$. The criterion photoresponse of the rod may be chosen freely in the linear range of responses. Thus, if Weber's law holds for the receptor responses, a spot on a uniform screen reflecting somewhat more than the screen gives the same response (to the step of light stimulus) in any illumination when the gaze is turned to that spot.

Weber's law is approximately obeyed and the response range preserved if the transmitter coefficient Q depends on the background intensity according to the equation

$$Q = \frac{Q_0}{1 + I_B/I_D}, \quad (4)$$

where Q_0 is the value of Q in the dark-adapted state. Even if Q decreases less than indicated by Eq. 4 Weber's law would hold approximately but the maximum photoresponse would decrease continually with increasing background intensity.

Light-adaptation, i.e. the Q -decrease, should start when the background light is still so weak that it has not yet reduced U_{\max} too much. On the other hand, the reduction of Q should not start by a too weak background light, as the decrease of Q increases the threshold. A suitable value of I_D in Eq. 4 is 0.1–0.4 I_h , corresponding to the maximum responses $U_{\max} = 0.9$ – $0.7 U_m$ in the light-adapted state. In other words, the «dark light» of the rod, I_D , should be 0.4–1 log units smaller than the half maximum intensity of the dark-adapted rod.

Comparison of experimental results and theory

The experimentally observed displacements of the operating curve for frog rods at differ-

Fig. 3. Stationary operating curves at 9°C in darkness and at six relative background illuminations $\log I_{Brel} = 0-5$. $\log I_{Brel} = 0$ corresponds to the bleaching rate $3 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Flash stimuli: $\log I_{rel} = 0$ corresponds to the fraction $8 \cdot 10^{-10}$ bleached. Step of light stimuli: $\log I_{rel} = 0$ corresponds to the bleaching rate $2 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ s}^{-1}$. CP is the crossing point of the asymptotih lines. (From Hemilä, ref. 28)

ent background intensities (28) may be summarized as follows (Figs. 3 and 4):

1) The shape of the operating curve deviates somewhat from that predicted by Eq. 2. However, when varying I_B the shape of the curve is unchanged, although large displacements are observed.

2) The displacement of the operating curve caused by the background light is predominantly to the right but also somewhat downwards (Fig. 3).

3) The displacements are such that the criterion threshold coarsely obeys Weber's law. However, log threshold rises clearly somewhat less than expected according to Eq. 3.

4) When stimulating with flashes of light the curve I_t vs. I_B deviates from Eq. 3 somewhat more than when step of light stimuli are used.

5) The adaptation to a new level of background light is fast but not instantaneous. In the dark the threshold I_t returns to I_0 in about half a minute.

6) According to the stimulus intensity calibration based on the bleaching rate (28) and assuming $1.5 \cdot 10^9$ rhodopsin molecules per rod (19) the intensity value of the crossing point in the dark is typically $I_h = 3$ photoisomerizations in a second per rod ($\text{Rh}^+ \text{ sec}^{-1}/\text{rod}$) and the typical asymptotic onset of the threshold rise is $I_D = 0.4 \text{ Rh}^+ \text{ sec}^{-1}/\text{rod}$.

Fain has obtained fairly similar results when studying intracellularly toad rods (23). An average value of the flash sensitivity was $U_m/I_h = 642 \mu\text{V}/\text{Rh}^+$. The intracellular max-

imum responses were somewhat above 10 mV, and thus the crossing point intensity for the flash stimuli in toad is roughly 20 Rh^+/rod . Thus using a value 2 sec for the integrating time of the step of light (6) gives the crossing point intensity corresponding to step stimuli, $I_h = 10 \text{ Rh}^+ \text{ sec}^{-1}/\text{rod}$. The value of I_D was $4.2 \text{ Rh}^+ \text{ sec}^{-1}/\text{rod}$.

The displacements of the operating curve brought about by small background lights $I_B < 100 I_h$ can be explained quantitatively on the basis of the simple model outlined above, assuming that the decrease of Q is the sole adaptation process (28). In addition to the large displacement to the right, the curve also moves progressively downwards. This is to be expected if Q decreases somewhat less than in the case of Eq. 4. The asymptotic onset of the threshold rise is $I_D \approx 0.13 I_h$, in agreement with the line of argument presented above. In toads the ratio is somewhat larger, $I_D \approx 0.4 I_h$ (23).

The threshold I_t returns to I_0 in about half a minute when the background is removed. Thus the »after-state» in the outer segment brought about by a photoisomerization lasts roughly during that time. Consequently, in the background light $I_B = 0.4 \text{ Rh}^+ \text{ sec}^{-1}/\text{rod}$ there are in the stationary state on the average only about 12 discs out of ca. 1500 in each rod possessing such an »after-state». However, this background equals I_D and thus decrease Q to $1/2 Q_0$! This means that the effect caused by the background light is not limited only to those discs which have absorbed quanta. Possibly, the discs possessing an »after-state» release some molecules which

Fig. 4. Log threshold versus log background intensity at 9°C. Triangles: the experiment shown in Fig. 3. Circles: an experiment in another retina. The curves: $I_t/I_0 = 1 + (I_B/I_D)^\beta$. Note slightly displaced scales for better fitting of the curves. The chosen I_D values for each set of experimental points vary slightly: the first point of each set corresponds to the same background, $\log I_{Brel} = 0$. (From Hemilä, ref. 28)

drastically decrease the q -value of many neighbouring discs.

If the decrease of Q were the only adaptation process in the rod, the curve $\log I_t$ versus $\log I_B$ would have a slope β equal to or above one. In Fig. 4 this slope is below one in the whole range of background intensities. As interpreted according to the model, this result indicates the appearance of a *sensitizing process* at more intense backgrounds: the quanta of the transient stimulus light are more effective in eliciting rod hyperpolarization than the quanta of the stationary background light. The process involved is not known, but it is possible that the transient increase of the potassium conductance of the rod inner segment because of the hyperpolarization could cause such sensitization. The existence of this kind of regenerative hyperpolarization was suggested by Brown and Pinto (12), and Werblin (43) studied such a process in *Necturus* rods in detail.

The values $\beta < 1$ due to the sensitization seems to contradict the argument that Weber's law is a functional law. However, besides this goal — the constancy of contrasts in familiar surroundings — a competing functional goal is clearly to observe as effectively

When seeking that goal, the proper relation between $\log I_t$ and $\log I_B$ is $I_t \propto \sqrt{I_B}$ corresponding to $\beta = 1/2$, as pointed out by Barlow as possible sudden weak events far away. (2). In that case the signal-to-noise ratio is constant when the noise is due to the quantal nature of the light. To pursue this goal at least a certain fraction of rods needs a mechanism for the amplification of the transient signals, and this seems to be the case. The constant-contrasts goal applies especially to large visual fields and long exposures (step of light stimuli), while the efficiency to observe sudden distant events applies specifically to small fields and flash stimuli. In support with this line of argument, Barlow and Levick (3) have observed in ganglion cell recordings of the cat values $\beta = 0.8-1$ in the case of large fields and long stimuli, but $\beta \approx 0.5$ in the case of small fields and flash stimuli. The differences of rod responses in frogs to step of light stimuli and flash stimuli in Fig. 4 serve these goals at the receptor level. The neural network after the rods can then pursue both goals. According to the ganglion cell recordings of Donner and Reuter (19), $\beta = 1$ for three log units of I_B in the frog when using step of light stimuli and

Fig. 5. Dark-adaptation curves for two ganglion cells. Opened eye of the frog, 13°C. Curve B after a strong light-adaptation, curve D after a 60 sec exposure which bleached ca. 6% of rhodopsin. Curve C: relative values for the numbers of quanta absorbed at threshold during dark-adaptation after the strong exposure (curve B). Curve A: the course of regeneration of rhodopsin under the conditions for curve B. (Donner and Reuter, ref. 18).

the stimulus field was relatively large (0.35 mm on the retina).

The absolute sensitivity of the rod in the dark-adapted state is very high indeed. In the case of flash stimuli, the crossing point intensity is about 10 Rh⁺/rod (Fig. 3). Thus a flash isomerizing on the average one rhodopsin per rod triggers a process which elicits a hyperpolarization about a tenth of the maximum response. The same order of magnitude of the quantum response, about 0.05 U_m, has been observed in the toad (23). Of course, these values do not mean that the range of rod vision is only one log unit. Even the *intracellularly* recorded photoresponses from a rod are proportional to the flash intensity at weak stimulus intensities, when each rod absorbs less than one photon per flash (23, 25). This spreading of excitation is due to the interreceptor contacts (5, 22). Moreover, each ganglion cell receives and adds signals from many rods, thus measuring the average stimulus intensity received by these rods. For instance, in the frog more than 2000 rod cells are coupled to a single class 3 ganglion cell having a large excitatory receptive field. If the criterion for that ganglion cell were four excitations in its receptive field (the order of magnitude of the absolute threshold observed psychophysically in man), the threshold intensity of that ganglion cell

would be less than 0.002 Rh⁺/rod. At low intensities the individual rods would receive at the most one quantum per flash (or per the integrating time), and most of them none. With increasing intensity the response of the ganglion cell soon reaches saturation. Thus in this range of intensities a network adaptation is needed, a mechanism which moves the operating curve of the ganglion cell to the right when increasing the background light. The inhibitory lateral connections in the neuronal network of the retina are able to produce such displacement, and the conditions leading to Weber's law can also be fulfilled (28). This kind of neuronal network also causes the threshold rise observed in psychophysical studies using weak background lights (40).

The light-adaptation ability of the rods varies in different species. The rods of the frogs and the toads adapt effectively, but the range of adaptation in, for example, *Necturus* rods is rather limited (35). If the range of measurable intensities of the rods and the cones overlap in the dark-adapted state, little Q-adaptation is needed in the rods. Large horizontal displacements of the operating curve have been invariably observed in the cones (see e.g. ref. 35). This is to be expected, as the range of intensities which the cones detect is very large in usual circumstances.

Fig. 6. Movements of the operating curve of frog rods during dark-adaptation. Receptor potentials were measured in two isolated retinas at 9°C, and the crossing points were determined (see Fig. 3). First bleach: open circles, second bleach: filled circles, third bleach: crosses. Amounts bleached: A: 8—9 %, B: 23, 23, and 28 %. Times after the bleach are indicated along some experimental points. (Bäckström and Hemilä, to be published.)

The skate has only rods in its retina, and, correspondingly, these rods adapt very effectively to the background light: Weber's law holds for six decades (21).

DARK-ADAPTATION

After a weak exposure or a light-adaptation period bleaching less than say 1 % of rhodopsin a fairly fast return to the dark-adapted state is observed. *Dark-adaptation* in customary usage means the slow recovery processes observed after stronger exposures leading to moderate or large bleaches. Fig. 5 shows the returns of the ganglion cell threshold in an opened eye of the frog after a 6 % bleach and a nearly complete bleach at 13°C (18). After a fast cone branch an *intermediate adaptation* transient is first observed: the log threshold decreases approximately exponen-

tially towards a plateau. The slower final return of the threshold intensity (pronounced after the large bleach) is here called *opsin adaptation* because it is apparently correlated with the regeneration of rhodopsin. In isolated frog retinas without pigment epithelium, and thus with a very limited regeneration capacity, *permanent changes* are observed instead of the opsin adaptation: after the bleach and the intermediate adaptation period threshold remains above the absolute threshold and the maximum response is reduced. The decreased absorption due to bleached rhodopsin (decreased quantum catch) is a minor contribution in the threshold elevation observed during the opsin adaptation (Fig. 9).

It is difficult to see any functional advantage in the long-lasting impairment of the receptors after large bleaches. Thus it is probable that such large bleaches simply overload

Fig. 7. The time courses of dark-adaptation and the decays of metarhodopsin III and metarhodopsin II + »bound retinal» after a 7.2 % bleach at 9°C. Isolated frog retina, perfused with aspartate. (Donner and Hemilä, unpublished.)

some of the processes in the chain of events leading from the absorption of the photons to the excitation of the ganglion cell. In the natural environment, even in bright sunlight, rhodopsin is never bleached to an extent that corresponds to the bleaching observed under experimental conditions.

Assuming that the shape of the operating curve remains constant during dark-adaptation, the movement of the operating curve may be followed by measuring in turns photoresponses to weak and strong stimuli. Fig. 6 shows examples of such movements after successive bleaches in two frog retinas, bleaches 8—9 % in one retina and above 20 % in another. The end points of the paths, the permanent displacements, are predominantly to the right and increase cumulatively from one bleach to the next. The movement of the operating curve during intermediate adaptation follows a curved path which is fairly horizontal after a first small bleach but which gets more oblique in successive bleaches. In the case of larger bleaches the first path is already rather oblique, and the last path is nearly vertical. As interpreted according to the adaptation model, these results indicate the dominant role of the Q -adaptation (changes in the parameter Q), both in intermediate adaptation and opsin adaptation in »endurable conditions», i.e. after bleaching

some 10 % or less of rhodopsin in the initially non-bleached retina (the first, small bleach). In these conditions the time course of the log threshold increase may be used as an estimate of the horizontal displacement of the operating curve, which in turn is approximately equal to the decrease of $\log Q$. After larger bleaches several different processes seem to contribute to the displacement of the operating curve, rendering interpretation of the time course of the intermediate adaptation rather difficult.

If the threshold rise in the »endurable conditions» is caused by the decrease of Q , the intermediate adaptation mechanism should be searched in the discs of the rods. Similarly to the background adaptation an »after-state» following the bleach causes a reduction in the transmitter release factor q . When looking for a suitable »after-state», a simple candidate is the long-lived intermediate photoproduct of rhodopsin. In Fig. 7 the time courses of dark-adaptation and the decay of MIII, and MII + »bound retinal» (see 17) are shown (Donner and Hemilä, unpublished). The similarity of the time courses of log threshold and the amount of bound retinal is qualitatively apparent. This result corresponds to the quantitative analysis of the dark-adaptation on the ganglion cell level carried out by

Fig. 8. Dark-adaptation and the photoproduct decay in crucian carp retinas. Triangles (cones) and dots (rods) give ganglion cell threshold in the eye cup preparates after bleaching 2.5 % of the porphyropsin. The open circles give measurements of the decay of the last intermediate photoproduct (400 nm product) as measured on the isolated retina. (From Donner, ref. 16).

Donner and Reuter (19). However, the correlation of the log threshold rise (or the horizontal displacement of the operating curve) and the amount of the long-lived photoproduct is somewhat ambiguous, because it is not possible to isolate accurately enough the process affecting the Q-parameter from the side processes which contribute to intermediate adaptation or cause the permanent changes. Thus it would help to elucidate the position to look for experimental conditions which affect the photoproduct kinetics, and to find out the corresponding changes in the electrophysiological threshold. Such conditions may include the temperature, species, length of the bleaching period, type of the receptor, and suitable drugs.

The decay kinetics of the porphyropsin photoproducts of the rods in the crucian carp eye are different from those in the frog, in that no metarhodopsin III appears during the decay. Anyway, the time courses of the last intermediate and the log threshold are nearly identical, as seen in Fig. 8 (16). In the same figure it is seen that increasing temperature speeds both time courses equally effectively.

If a given amount of rhodopsin is bleached slowly, a considerable fraction of the last intermediate photoproduct decays to opsin during the bleach. Thus, if the threshold increase is caused by the photo-product, the magnitude of the intermediate adaptation transient after bleaching a certain fraction of rhodopsin should be effectively diminished by

Fig. 9. Permanent threshold rises of the receptor potential isolated with aspartate (or by intracellular techniques) in several species. 1 and 2: *Rana temporaria*, 9°C and 14°C respectively (Bäckström and Hemilä, unpublished), 3: *Rana pipiens*, 22°C (31), 4: Axolotl, 24°C, intracellular techniques (25), 5: Skate, 27°C (9), 6: *Rana catesbeiana*, 23°C (33), 7: Carp, a single point (44), 8: The calculated quantum catch curve — $\log(1 - \Delta R)$, when ΔR is the fraction of rhodopsin bleached.

increasing the duration of the bleach. This reduction has indeed been observed in frog rods (30).

Cones and green rods of the frog return to the dark-adapted state much faster than the ordinary red rods. Unfortunately, lack of experimental data prevents a correlation of intermediate adaptation and the long-lived photoproducts in these photoreceptors. In the case of opsin adaptation the green rods and the red rods may be compared (20). Both the dark-adaptation and the regeneration of photopigment are much faster in the green than in red rods.

The relation between bleached rhodopsin and the permanent threshold rise of the rods for several species is shown in Fig. 9. The logarithmic presentation is based on the log scales used in the operating curve diagram. The general shape of the different curves is rather similar: log threshold increase is proportional to the fraction of rhodopsin bleached up to bleaches of about 20%, but at larger bleaches the threshold rises slower. The experimental curves correspond rather well to a linear increase of the threshold intensity with the amount bleached, especially when the absorbed threshold intensities are used, as earlier noted by Gordon and Hood (24). Quantitatively, however, the curves in Fig. 9 differ considerably from each other. The comparison of curves 1 and 2 indicate that the temperature affects the threshold rises quite strongly. It appears that the curves for

different species were fairly close to each other, provided that the receptor potentials of each species are measured in the physiological temperature of that species. However, some other conditions also affect the permanent threshold rises (cf. curves 3 and 6 in Fig. 9).

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